

Rationale & Analysis

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As a consultant for the chosen government agency, the paper would thoroughly review the goals, objectives, functions and current activities at the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). The purpose of this paper is to clearly highlight the functions and objectives of the agency. The rationale and importance of the chosen agency would be discussed in detail to provide a thorough understanding of the agency's role in the American society.

Interview with the Director of Operations at FDA

In order to gain insight on FDA's operations, its involvement in research and latest developments; an interview was conducted with the Director of Operations at FDA's head office. The interview was pre-scheduled and was conducted on the phone. The Director of Operations was very helpful in providing us with relevant information for the completion of this assignment. Also, the insight and latest information on the agency's endeavors allowed us to better understand the operations of the agency and to draw relevant inferences.

Food & Drug Administration (FDA)

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) is a governmental agency which works under the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. The FDA comprises of four directorates and the Commissioner's Office; who are responsible for overseeing the major functions of the agency. The FDA is responsible for the regulation of Foods, Tobacco, Medical Products and Veterinary Medicine (Heath, Andrews & Balkstra, 2004). The head office of U.S Food and Drug Administration is located at 10903 New Hampshire Avenue, Silver Spring 20993. The FDA is

one of the major executive federal departments. The agency is responsible for the promotion and protection of public health in the United States.

History

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) is the oldest consumer protection agency of the United States' Federal government. It was done to conduct chemical analyses on agricultural drugs and products. It was a function which was introduced in the year 1862. The name of the process was not finalized until the 1930s (FDA, 2014).

The agency's modern regulatory functions started in the year 1906 under the Pure Food and Drugs Act. It was a law which took over 25 years for its implementation. The aim of the law was to counter issues of misbranded and adulterated foods and drugs. It is because of the agency's efforts and focus that consumers are protected from flawed foods and drugs in the United States.

Mission, Goals & Objectives

The prime responsibility of FDA is the protection of public safety and regulation of veterinary and medical drugs, medical devices, biological products, cosmetics and foods.

- Taking initiatives for the advancement of public health. The agency does so by conducting research to make the medicines safer and more effective. Hence, the role of FDA is vital to providing safe and healthy foods and medicines to Americans.
- The manufacturing, regulation, distribution and marketing of tobacco products is overseen by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA).

The FDA also plays an evident role in ensuring the nation's counterterrorism capability. The agency performs the function by fulfilling its responsibilities of ensuring quality food supply and assisting the development of medicines in dealing with public health issues.

Agency Functions

According to FDA's website (2013), the following are the main functions of FDA:

1. Protection of public health by assuring the effectiveness, safety, security and quality of drugs. The safety and security of the country's dietary supplements, food products and cosmetics is also regulated by FDA.
2. Regulation of Tobacco products and their distribution
3. Ensuring research for better public health and controlling the spread of diseases

Current Events involving implications to Personnel Management

Diagnosing Cancer

Presently, the scientists at FDA are working on the screening and diagnosis of cancer by employing the use of 3D imagery. The agency Scientists at the Food and Drug Administration believe that it would allow doctors to timely and accurately diagnose cancers. Due to the complexity of the feat, competent personnel trained in dealing with 3D imagery has become an issue for FDA.

Over the Counter Drugs

Another research involving personnel management issues is the agency's latest endeavor of assessing the impact of over the counter medicines on driving. Due to the legal complexities in its testing, FDA is presently facing issues in obtaining willing candidates for its research.

Rationale

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) is a vital component of the United States' governmental infrastructure. The distinct role of the agency is multifaceted and quite complicated. The main reason behind choosing FDA was due to its involvement and authority in the food and medicine sector.

It should be noticed that the FDA also looks over the controversial issues of patents. The patent rights of a drug allow the developers the right to exclusively manufacture and sell a given drug. Issues of patents often lead to legal battles between companies. Hence, the monetary element in FDA's involvement cannot be denied.

The main reasons for choosing FDA were to highlight the importance of the agency and the role it plays in ensuring the health of Americans. FDA continues to be the prime authority in the development, production and sales of a vast array of drugs. Considering the involvement of the agency in different tiers of government institutions; the agency was carefully selected for analysis.

References

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